

***o*-Aldehydocarboxylic Acids. Part I. A New General Method of Synthesising Phthalonic Acids. A Synthesis of ψ -Opianic Acid and a New Synthesis of *m*-Opianic Acid.**

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In an earlier paper one of us (S. N. C.) had pointed out that there were very few really good methods available for the synthesis of *o*-aldehydocarboxylic acids and a new general method of synthesising these acids starting from symmetrically di- and tetrasubstituted derivatives of naphthalene was described (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 693). The difficulty about this new method is that the starting materials for these acids are not yet readily available substances, and we have, therefore, devised another method of synthesising these acids. The method consists in oxidising homophthalic acid with an equimolecular quantity of selenium dioxide in boiling xylene solution when the corresponding phthalonic acid is obtained in excellent yields. The phthalonic acid is then converted into the corresponding *o*-aldehydocarboxylic acid through its sodium bisulphite compound under the conditions previously described by one of us (*loc. cit.*). Homophthalic acids being readily available substances (*cf.* Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1082; Ingold and Pigott, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 1476; Haworth, Perkin and Stevens, *ibid.*, 1926, 1764; Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 101), this new method of synthesis should prove to be a valuable one.

ψ -Opianic acid (I), for the synthesis of which numerous unsuccessful attempts have been made in the past (*cf.* Solomon, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 888; Perkin and Stoyl, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3173; Edwards, Perkin and Stoyl, *ibid.*, 1925, 196; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 208; Robinson, "On life and work of Perkin", p. 80) and which has been recently obtained by Robinson and Greenwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 137) by the oxidation of β -pseudognoscopine, has now been synthesised by an application of this method. 5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (II) was oxidised in boiling xylene solution by means of selenium dioxide to 5:6-dimethoxyphthalonic acid (III). The phthalonic acid was then converted into ψ -opianic acid under conditions described in the experimental section,

The acid thus obtained had all the properties of ψ -opianic acid obtained by Perkin by the hydrolysis of berberal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 1064). For confirmation of its identity it was reduced to ψ -me-coine (m.p. 124°) and also converted into its oxime (m.p. 125°), and hemipinimide. The mixed melting points of these derivatives with the corresponding authentic specimens showed no depression.

In a similar manner, opianic acid (IV), which had previously been synthesised by tedious methods (*cf.* Fargher and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1724; Perkin and Stoye, *loc. cit.*; Perkin, Edwards and Stoye, *loc. cit.*), has now been obtained from 4:5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (V) in an excellent yield.

A number of other phthalonic acids have been similarly synthesised and an account of the syntheses of all the methoxy and methylenedioxy-*o*-aldehydicarboxylic acids is reserved for a future communication.

Another interesting method of converting homophthalic acids to *o*-phthalaldehyde acids has also been discovered. When a homophthalic acid is treated with 4 molecules of phosphorus pentachloride, a tetrachloro compound is formed which on hydrolysis gives rise to the corresponding phthalonic acid. The latter acid can then be converted into the corresponding *o*-aldehydicarboxylic acid. Thus ψ -opianic acid, which had resisted all previous attempts at synthesis, has now been synthesised in the following manner:—

EXPERIMENTAL.

As a result of a series of comparative experiments, the following condition of oxidation was arrived at as giving the best yield of the phthalonic acids from the corresponding homophthalic acids.

The homophthalic acid (1 mol.) was suspended in dry xylene (generally 100 c. c. for 1 g. of the acid) and the mixture heated to boiling. Selenium dioxide (1 mol.) was then added to the boiling xylene solution and boiling continued for 5 to 8 hours. After the oxidation, the xylene solution and the insoluble residues were thoroughly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the combined extracts made just acid with concentrated hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath. The residue which contained the free phthalonic acid together with inorganic and other substances were worked up differently in different cases.

The phthalonic acids, which were generally isolated as aniline derivatives or directly converted into o-aldehydocarboxylic acids, were obtained thus in yields varying from 50 to 80%. Longer boiling with selenium dioxide in xylene solution or boiling with excess of selenium dioxide did not improve the yields in majority of the cases.

ψ-Opianic acid.—5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (5 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (500 c.c.) and the mixture heated to boiling. To the boiling mixture, selenium dioxide (3 g.) was added and the boiling continued for 3 hours. During this process the homophthalic acid gradually went into solution and a reddish solution, containing a black deposit of selenium, was obtained. The mixture was thoroughly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the combined extracts just acidified and evaporated to dryness. The residue was then taken up in boiling water (50 c.c.), filtered from a little insoluble matter and the filtrate treated with excess of sodium bisulphite solution and evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath and then heated for half an hour at 120° in an air oven. The residue thus obtained was twice stirred up with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness

on a steam-bath. This residue was then extracted twice with boiling benzene and from the combined benzene extract the solvent removed by distillation. The residual oil was heated on the steam-bath with aniline (4 c.c.) for 10 minutes. On adding a little methyl alcohol and scratching, the aniline derivative separated. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol, it was obtained as beautiful silky needles, m.p. 187°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.3. The aniline derivative of ψ -opianic acid $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 67.4; H, 5.3 per cent).

The aniline derivative (1 g.) was heated with dilute hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) on the steam-bath for 1½ hours. On cooling an acid separated in wooly needles, which on being recrystallised from water and dried on a water-bath melted at 121-22°. (Found: C, 57.5; 57.6; H, 5.0, 5.1. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

The acid was reduced under conditions similar to those used by Perkin for reducing ψ -opianic acid to ψ -meconine, when a substance, m.p. 124°, identical in all respects with ψ -meconine, was obtained.

On treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride under conditions described by Perkin (*loc. cit.*), it gave rise to an oxime, m.p. 124°, identical with the oxime of ψ -opianic acid.

5:6-Dimethoxy-3:3:4:4-tetrachloro-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII).—5:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (3.6 g.), mixed with phosphorus pentachloride (12.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 g.) was heated for 8 hours at 140-150°. The phosphorus oxychloride was removed under reduced pressure from a water-bath and the residue was treated with cold water, when a solid separated. This solid on crystallisation from methyl alcohol gave (VII) in beautiful prisms, m.p. 128°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 38.3, 38.37; H, 2.46, 2.41; Cl, 40.96, 41.0. $C_{11}H_8O_4Cl_4$ requires C, 38.2; H, 2.3; Cl, 41.0 per cent). This chloro compound is readily soluble in ordinary solvents and is remarkably stable towards water and methyl alcohol.

Conversion of (VII) to ψ -opianic acid.—The tetrachloroisocoumarin (1 g.) was added to methyl alcoholic potash (2 g. dissolved in 50 c.c. of methyl alcohol) and refluxed for 8 hours on the steam bath. The methyl alcohol was then completely removed and the residue dissolved in water. The solution was made just acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was taken up in 10 c.c. of 40 % sodium bisulphite and the sodium bisulphite compound on being treated in the manner described earlier gave an aniline derivative (0.6 g.), m.p. 187°, and an aldehydo-acid, m.p. 121-22°, which were

found to be identical with the aniline derivative of ψ -opianic acid and with ψ -opianic acid respectively, and the mixed melting points showed no depression.

m-Opianic acid—(i). 4:6-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (5 g.) was oxidised with selenium dioxide under conditions described in the case of 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid and crude phthalonic acid, obtained in the manner described under the general method, was taken up in 100 c.c. of boiling water and treated with aniline (4 c.c.). The mixture was heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour when the aniline salt of 4:5-dimethoxyphthalonic acid separated in an excellent yield (4 g.). The aniline derivative crystallises from methyl alcohol in glistening laminae, m.p. 179-80°. The aniline derivative on being treated in the manner described for *m*-opianic acid by Perkin and Fargher (*loc. cit.*) gave an acid, m.p. 187-88°, which was identical in all its properties with *m*-opianic acid. (Found: C, 56.7; H, 5.0. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

(ii) When the oxidation in xylene solution was carried out for 8 hours and the product worked up as before, the yield of the aniline derivative was 5 g.

(iii) When the oxidation was continued for 16 hours, the final yield was a little over 5 g.

Oxidation of homophthalic acid.—Homophthalic acid was prepared according to the method described by Ingold and Pigott (*loc. cit.*) and oxidised under 3 different conditions described in the previous case. The following yields of the aniline derivative of the phthalonic acid were obtained:—

(i) Boiling in xylene solution with selenium dioxide for 3 hours. From 5 g. of the homophthalic acid 3 g. of the aniline derivative, m.p. 166°, was obtained.

(ii) When the boiling was continued for 8 hours, the yield of the aniline derivative was 2.5 g.

(iii) When the boiling was continued for 16 hours, the yield of the aniline derivative was reduced to 2 g.

